

JPL Open Sourced Science (OSS) for NASA Earth System Observatory (ESO) Mission Science Data Processing Study Request for Information (RFI) GEC-2680-12152021

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About Element 84

Element 84 is a women-owned software development firm that builds ambitious web applications and cloud services engineered for high scalability. We work with public and private sector clients to create systems that help solve problems and answer big questions about our health, our infrastructure, and our changing planet.

We have over a decade of experience as a trusted partner in the Earth science and geospatial communities helping satellite operators, universities, and organizations like NASA, NOAA, and the USGS create systems, software, and user experiences that make their data more actionable and accessible.

Related Experience and Expertise

- 11 years of experience in Earth science and geospatial supporting NASA, NOAA, USGS, and the NSF
- 2017 Goddard Space Flight Center Mentor-Protege of the Year Awardee (Protege)
- Full stack expertise (system architecture, engineering, design and UX, devops, and technical leadership)
- Architecture, design, and implementation of NASA Cumulus, the cloud-based ingest, management, and distribution system for the EOSDIS data archive
- OPeNDAP development on MODIS and ASTER satellite products for NASA and USGS's Earth Resources Observation and Science Center
- Ongoing partnerships with commercial satellite operators and SAR imagery producers
- Leadership positions and contributions within the open geospatial community including SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC), OGC, and multiple industry working groups within Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP)

Topic Area 1. Data Processing System Architecture

Element 84’s experience helping downstream consumers of geospatial data has led us to identify a demonstrable need for an approachable solution to automating and scaling data processing workflows. We recommend promoting the use of metadata-first workflows, offering a seamless and automated experience through data production, discovery, access, analysis, and surfacing of results.

Efforts are being made to make heterogeneous data analysis easier (e.g., Analysis Ready Data (ARD) and pre-aligned data products such as Harmonized Landsat Sentinel (HLS)). However, data processing systems remain stovepiped and are often “industrial strength” solutions with complex deployment and environmental dependencies. Projects like HySDS¹ and NASA Cumulus² have been successfully reused within NASA and even across agencies—with NOAA’s adoption of Cumulus. A lesser-served audience is the open source science community and lab environments that operate at a smaller scale than NASA data providers and DAACs. Our recommended open source science approach is the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC³) for describing geospatial data, search and discovery queries, and processing workflows executed by the open source Cirrus⁴ project. Supported by a growing ecosystem of open-source tools, STAC workflows bundle metadata along with data location and access information, processing steps and validation, and a trail of data provenance. The resulting STAC catalog can be consumed by end users in notebooks, visualization tools, and further downstream processing. Cirrus—originating from a NASA ACCESS grant—is an open source STAC-based cloud processing pipeline that facilitates small-to-large scale geospatial data processing. The key components of the underlying tooling are scalable, elastic, parallel processing, real-time state and progress tracking, projected and real cost estimation, and multi-cloud support. Cirrus is deployed operationally to support open data, commercial data, and downstream data analysis.

Our recommendation for NASA is to enable end-to-end data analysis workflows, starting from NASA science quality data production through end user data analysis and automation, by:

1. Producing “use-oriented” metadata from the start. STAC metadata catalogs—which can be largely (and often automatically) derived from existing NASA metadata—offer current best-in-class end-user support.
2. Supporting tooling and infrastructure that enables downstream users to efficiently—and in an automated manner—leverage NASA-produced data. This can be facilitated by making available typical processing and analysis workflows in a stand-alone manner with appropriate STAC workflow metadata. Containers provide an excellent mechanism for distributing these capabilities and—coupled with task-based workflow descriptions that can be leveraged by small and medium scale workflow engines—are ideal building blocks.

Please see Page 6, Links to Publicly Available Publications and Relevant Resources that Support the Response, for footnote references.

Topic Area 2. Open Science

Reproducibility is a cornerstone of science. Enabling hypotheses to be systematically tested by independent researchers allows for the clear and direct sharing of scientific information and knowledge. Within the field of remote sensing, reproducibility is extremely challenging. Data size, restrictive data access, customized pre-processing workflows, and opaque algorithms make reproducing results challenging or impossible. Fully realizing the benefits of the expanding archive of Earth observation data—while preserving reproducibility—will require a suite of related standards and technologies focused on 1) increased storage and processing efficiency; 2) comprehensive and automatic metadata accounting; 3) shared workflows and computing environments; and 4) version control of science itself.

A critical facilitator of a cloud-native approach is to host Earth observation data in cloud-optimized formats and to describe and index the data with systematic, use-oriented metadata—such as that provided by the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification⁵. The goal of STAC is to provide a common language for describing the characteristics and provenance of geospatial data, such that it can be effectively indexed and discovered by users. Data indexed by a STAC API can be flexibly queried and represents a change in emphasis from handling and processing the files themselves to using the metadata as the *handle* with which to hold the data. A STAC-powered workflow implicitly maintains the original metadata, as well as adding to it (e.g. links to cloud storage locations of outputs, storing processing steps and provenance) and creating searchable output catalogs.

An *executable paper*—a peer-reviewed research publication that includes the full analytical workflow and any requisite data hosted in the cloud—would allow a person to replicate the data management, processing, and analytical steps involved in a study, and independently verify and interpret the results. This technique is possible through the use of online notebooks such as Jupyter notebooks. However, such notebooks can be made far more powerful by technologies that facilitate the sharing of entire computational environments, such as JupyterHub⁶. While sharing code via notebooks is a powerful means of increasing transparency and openness, they do not solve the problem of reproducibility entirely. JupyterHub allows for the sharing of pre-defined computing environments in the cloud, where they are close to the data, thereby reducing the technical barrier to entry for researchers seeking to run a workflow. Building on this, BinderHub⁷ allows such environments to be containerized and easily shared. Open licensing is a critical element of open science, including ideas, text, and code. Such licensing will enable scientists to share advances, while protecting the authors' intellectual property and ensuring that scientific ideas and code are used as the authors intend, whether that means permissive usage, such as allowed under the MIT License, or more controlled copyleft usage, such as with the GPL License.

Software, data, and research publications greatly benefit from version control. Shared JupyterHub environments can help address software versioning issues, and data versioning should be addressed by explicit version control of input datasets—using a specification like the STAC version extension⁸. Workflows can be pinned to the analysis and interpretations within the peer-reviewed materials. This is becoming ever more critical as algorithms and datasets are shared and iterated on with greater frequency.

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Topic Area 3. Component Technologies

The wide availability of Earth science system data is necessary—but not sufficient—for efficient use by scientists and researchers. Because of the milieu of data sources and providers, there is a need for software and standards that can operate on geoscience data that vary in type, quality, metadata, and more. A developing suite of *component technologies* exploit commonalities between data to enhance discovery, access, and analysis, both during development and at scale.

At the asset level, the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) metadata standard⁹ provides a common structure to describe geospatial assets. The STAC specification recently reached version 1.0, indicating a maturity level suitable for use in production environments. The foundational PySTAC library provides a Python API for direct access to STAC resources and is the core of a variety of downstream libraries, including an implementation of the STAC API¹⁰ for network-enabled asset search and discovery.

Once geospatial data are discovered, they must be efficiently and portably read into processing environments—whether on local hardware or on cloud computing. The *fsspec* Python library allows backend-agnostic access to resources on local filesystems or in remote storage on a variety of cloud providers, allowing for code reuse between cloud ecosystems. Data are often read into *xarray* datasets, which provide a suite of operations for subsetting, visualizing, and modifying multi-dimensional data. The *odc-stac* project provides one mechanism for converting a collection of STAC metadata into a geospatial-enabled *xarray*, ready for use in time-series analysis, visualization, or other algorithmic exploitation. If data are provided in cloud-optimized formats, such as Cloud Optimized GeoTIFFs (COGs) for rasters or Cloud Optimized Point Clouds (COPCs) for point clouds, they can be efficiently subsetted and fetched with range requests, reducing request throughput and saving money for researchers and data providers. Of course, the foundational GDAL¹¹ library is a key component of almost every open geospatial processing pipeline, and its sibling PDAL¹² extends similar capabilities to point cloud data.

In the past it was necessary to use High Performance Computing (HPC) data centers or other complex systems to handle large, parallel processing chains. The barriers to entry and steep learning curves of HPC usage are an obstacle to many researchers and projects. Now, *dask* and its sister project *dask-gateway* allow researchers to quickly scale their processing environment from a laptop to a large cluster running in the cloud or on dedicated hardware. Even more accessibility is provided by JupyterHub and other hosted development environments, which allow the development and execution of code on remote systems, saving transfer costs by allowing the execution to reside next to the data themselves with little to no configuration required by the researcher.

These core component technologies are essential for open geoscience, and their continued support and improvement is necessary to continue open geoscience's extraordinary growth.

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Topic Area 4. Downstream Interoperability

Several new technologies are emerging in the modern geospatial world that aim to enable interoperability and ease of use of geospatial data. Datasets differ in their schema, format, structure, and processing that novel specifications and standards have emerged to achieve downstream interoperability such as Cloud Optimized Geotiffs (COGs¹³), Cloud Optimized Point Clouds (COPCs¹⁴), Discrete Global Grid Systems (DGGS¹⁵), and the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC¹⁶). A mission science data processing system should ideally generate data products and metadata that conform to these open standards and specifications. These structures can handle petabytes or exabytes of data, utilize smart data organization and indexing techniques to rapidly retrieve the objects of interest from a spatio-temporal query, and promote data standardization and harmonization of diverse data sources into a single, common framework.

COGs and COPCs are inherently cloud-native data specifications. COGs have been around since 2016 and allow for using regular GeoTIFF raster files on HTTP web servers so that clients can request them. Their specialty lies in the fact that by making an HTTP Range Request a client can request only portions of the TIFF file that it needs, thereby eliminating the need to download the entire file. COPC is a comparatively new data specification in which LIDAR point data is organized into the form of an octree, a data structure in which each internal node has 8 children nodes and leverages the open-source LAZ compressed point cloud storage format for storing variably-sized chunks of points. As they are cloud native formats, both COGs and COPCs offer the advantages of the cloud: preventing unnecessary duplication and copying of data, allowing global access, efficient streaming, elasticity, scalability and increased speed and agility.

A DGGS is a hierarchical tessellation of cells that covers the surface of the Earth at various resolutions. Now an Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) specification,¹⁷ DGGS is another means of achieving downstream interoperability by combining information from diverse sources in a single spatial reference system, enabling multi-source fusion. Each observation in a DGGS is associated with a single DGGS cell at a certain resolution, making it apt for ESO data ingestion as it provides a single common global framework for storage, aggregation, analysis, integration, and modeling.

Finally, the STAC metadata standard can be used for a range of geospatial information originating from diverse sources like imagery, SAR, point clouds, video, and more. The STAC API standard allows spatio-temporal queries to be performed against Items, Catalogs, and Collections. It is extensible, allowing contributors to extend the specification to suit the needs of the community by adding fields. The conversion of existing provisioned geospatial data into STAC and its delivery over the cloud (similar to COG and COPC) makes it searchable, crawlable, indexable, and accessible.

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- ¹ <https://hysds-core.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/HYS/overview>
- ² <https://nasa.github.io/cumulus/docs/cumulus-docs-readme>
- ³ <https://stacspec.org/>
- ⁴ <https://github.com/cirrus-geo/cirrus-geo>
- ⁵ <https://stacspec.org/>
- ⁶ <https://jupyter.org/hub>
- ⁷ <https://jupyter.org/binder>
- ⁸ <https://github.com/stac-extensions/version>
- ⁹ <https://stacspec.org>
- ¹⁰ <https://github.com/stac-utils/stac-fastapi>
- ¹¹ <https://gdal.org>
- ¹² <https://pdal.io>
- ¹³ <https://www.cogeo.org/in-depth.html>
- ¹⁴ <https://copc.io/>
- ¹⁵ <https://www.ogc.org/projects/groups/dggsswg>
- ¹⁶ <https://stacspec.org/why-stac.html>
- ¹⁷ <https://docs.opengeospatial.org/as/15-104r5/15-104r5.html>